

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

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Annotation: Language plays an important role in society, and each country has its own language units, and citizens speak these rules. The following linguistic units and technologies will be studied in the Department of Linguistics. This article is written on the differences between American and British English and is covered in full.

Keywords: linguistic features, American English, British English, history of words, lexical structure, grammatical structure, phonetic structure, dialectisms, slangisms, jargon, lexico- semantic differences.

Introduction

The language of any country is part of its culture. The modern language of international communication is English. It is a language spoken and written by hundreds of millions of people of different nationalities. It is the language of business, science, office work, information technology and, of course, the language of communication. English is the most studied language in the world, its influence is so huge that it can affect not only the vocabulary, but also the linguistic structure of other languages, so now more than a billion people on earth speak and strive to speak English.

Main Body

For many years, English in most countries, including Russia, was focused on the British version of the language, while the American language had to be mastered in practice, only for those who, in connection with their professional activities, needed to be and communicate with native American English speakers. At the present stage of the development of the English language, it is necessary to mention the fact that students (not only students, but also schoolchildren) are faced with the American version almost daily: they watch American films, listen to American music, read labels on American-made products and goods. Therefore, we must be competent in the differences between American and British languages. The significance of these two variants of the English language in modern society determines the relevance of our topic.

The purpose of the study is to systematize the linguistic differences between British and American English.

The goal is specified by the following tasks:

To study the question of the historical development of variants of the English language. Consider the concepts of linguistic variability and norms in the language system. Analyze the differences between American and British English at the phonetic, lexical, grammatical levels. To study the state of the problem in the scientific and methodological literature. The object of research is the lexical, grammatical, phonetic structure of the English language. The subject of the study is linguistic differences in the lexical, grammatical, phonetic structure of the British and American variants of the English language. [2. 43p] The theoretical significance of this work lies in the possibility of further using the results of the study when working with English texts, in the possibility of identifying and overcoming the difficulties of translating vocabulary, recognizing grammatical structures in understanding foreign speech by ear, pronounced both in British and American English. The practical significance of the study lies in the possibility of further application of the identified differences between the two variants of the English language, not only at school in the classroom, but also when working on a computer, searching for information in English-language sources.

History Of Variants Of The English Language

Just three centuries ago, there was only one type of English, it was spoken by the inhabitants of Foggy Albion. British colonizers, traders, travelers brought it to other continents, where it evolved, changed and enriched. New words appeared, pronunciation changed. The greatest changes in the English language have occurred in the Americas. If in Ireland, Australia, New Zealand there were more phonetic changes, then immigrants from different countries who settled in America also modified the grammar of the English language, making it simpler and easier. [3. Arakin, 2003] American English became the international language after World War II, when the United States assumed an important role in the post-war transformation of the world, and numerous achievements in politics, economics, and modern technology allowed the United States to have a huge impact on the whole world. Both sides, the Americans and the British, mutually laugh and dislike each other's languages. The British call American English too straightforward and rude, and they talk about their British English as the language of polite people. Americans, on the other hand, consider British English to be an overstretched, hypocritical language, and their native English to be welcoming and friendly.[3. G.B. Antrushina, 2004]

British English is the classic English that we learned in school. It was he who became the parent of American English, which is a dialect that has developed its

own characteristics. The differences between these two variants of the English language are due to the fact that the British, coming to new places, discovered new phenomena, such as previously unknown samples of flora and fauna, which had to be given names. The contacts of immigrants from the Old World with the local population also changed the English language. In addition, people of certain social groups and strata mostly recognized the new continent, which led to the fact that their English was already specific. Typical lexico-semantic differences between AE and BE. Within the framework of this article, it is not possible to give an exhaustive description of the distinctive features of the British and American lexico-semantic systems. In particular, we are forced to ignore the word-formation system and the area of idioms, which contain extensive material and require a separate study. The purpose of our work is to analyze the characteristic differences in the inventory composition of both systems. In the process of autonomous development of the American variant of the English language, a significant number of specific units were formed in its lexical-semantic system, which are commonly called Americanisms.

Results And Discussion

Americanisms are primarily classified into two categories: standard (literary) and non-standard (for example, dialectisms, slangisms, jargon, etc.). We confine ourselves to an analysis of standard Americanisms. [1.189P.] Life on the new continent greatly enriched the English language, brought a large number of neologisms. The settlers had to come up with new names for what they had not encountered before.

Among them, A.D. Schweitzer highlights the following:

1. neologisms associated with flora and fauna (moose - American elk, backwoods - wilderness, hickory - North American hazel, gap - mountain pass, deep gorge);
2. everyday neologisms (corn - corn, a lot - a piece of land);
3. neologisms associated with the way of life of the Indians (medicine man - the shaman of an Indian tribe, war-path - the warpath). [3. 28p].

There has been constant change in the vocabulary of the English language in America, as mentioned earlier, due to the formation of new words and due to borrowings from other languages.

1. First of all, it should be noted the quantitative difference in the total number of vowels: RP –20 [ɪ:, ɪ, u:, u, ɔ:, ɔ, æ, ʌ, a:, e, ə, ɜ:], [ɪə, eɪ, uə, ɔɪ, əu, eə, aɪ, aʊ]
GA – 16 [ɪ:, ɪ, u:, u, ɔ:, æ, ʌ, ɛ, a:, ə, , ɜ:], [eɪ, ɔɪ, əu, aɪ, ɔʊ].

The diphthongs [ɪə], [eə], [ʊə], realized in RP in the stressed position, as in the words near, hair, sure, are replaced in GA by [ɪr], [er], [ʊr] respectively.

RP: fear [fiə], here [hiə], pear [peə], care [keə], sure [ʃʊ:ɹ] GA: fear [fir], here [hir], care [ker], pear [per], sure [ʃur]

In English, as in other modern Indo-European languages, all forms existing in its system are divided into standard and non-standard. The standard form is the literary language taught in schools, used by the state media, and used in formal settings by the educated part of the population. Non-standard forms of the language are realized in regional and social dialects. Regional dialects are characteristic of the speech of the poorly educated part of the rural population. Social dialects are forms of language that are used in an informal setting by representatives of various social groups in the urban population. English in the modern world linguistic continuum. The English language has gained a dominant position in the modern world linguistic continuum due to two factors:

- the colonial expansion of the British Empire, which began with mass emigration to North America and reached its climax at the end of the First World War.
- the economic and political power of the United States in the second half of the twentieth century [4].

The global transplantation of the English language has led to the formation of its numerous regional variants, each of which is characterized by the presence of specific linguistic phenomena. In relation to the source of transplantation (English, formed in England), regional variants of the English language are divided into two groups [5]. The first group includes the so-called "old" variants (old English), which include:

- Australian English;
- American English;
- British English;
- Irish English;
- Canadian English ;
- New Zealand English.

Conclusion

To study the question of the linguistic features of American and British English, we set the following tasks:

1. To study the question of the historical development of the variants of the English language.

2. Consider the concepts of linguistic variability and norms in the language system.
3. Analyze the differences between American and British English at the phonetic, lexical, grammatical levels.
4. To study the state of the problem in the scientific and methodological literature.

Among the semantic differences, partial discrepancies in the semantic structure of the same words and differences in their use prevail. Quite indicative is the absence of significant structural discrepancies. In the field of morphology, these are mainly differences in individual word forms, and in the field of syntax and word formation, they are differences in the frequency of using the same constructions and word-formation models. All these data indicate the fundamental commonality of both variants of the English language.

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